

Research Article

The Buddy Finders

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Abstract: Buddy systems are important for diver's safety in many various aspects such as immediate assistance in emergencies, gear monitoring, backup in case of disorientation, navigation support, and much more. Various conditions such as weather, water pollution, and water movement like currents and waves could affect the visibility of water when diving making it easier for divers to lose contact with their buddy. Although there is a procedure to do when your buddy is missing, the procedure also takes some time and effort especially when the dive is too deep and it can cause some serious injuries in certain conditions. The product that we developed is a lightweight, affordable, convenient, and portable diving device to locate your buddy. This product offers a simple yet very effective way to locate your buddy and at the same time inform other details for a diver. "Buddy Finder" will provide an easier dive with its small, lightweight features yet very functioning. Overall, this product will upgrade the safety of divers and at the same time, be able to attract more people to take part in the scuba diving community.

Keywords: Buddy, Dive; Navigation; Buddy Finders; Safety;

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1. INTRODUCTION

Scuba diving is an aquatic activity that entails inhaling air from a tank while submerged. Scuba is an abbreviation for Self-Contained Underwater Breathing Apparatus (Ledford, 2023). The majority of scuba divers engage in recreational activities, exploring aquatic settings including lakes, rivers, quarries, kelp forests, and coral reefs (Zainal Abidin & Mohamed, 2014). Certain individuals engage in scuba diving for professional purposes, including public safety divers, marine biologists, and several others (Lucrezi et al., 2018).

Buddy diving is the practice of free divers and scuba divers using the buddy system. It is a safety protocol designed to increase divers' chances of surviving or avoiding underwater mishaps by requiring them to dive in groups of two, occasionally three (Gillespie, 2006). By diving together, group members who have adopted the buddy system are better able to assist or rescue one another in an emergency (Lillie, 2024).

This purpose is theoretically fulfilled by the buddy assisting the diver to kit up, checking that the diver's equipment is correctly assembled and mounted, assisting the diver into the water where appropriate, checking for leaks, monitoring gas usage, providing an alternate breathing gas supply in case of an emergency, performing a rescue if the diver is unable to manage an emergency, and assisting the diver out of the water after the dive if appropriate. This system can mitigate high-risk emergencies when performed to the standards.

1.1 Objective

The objective of the innovation project is to design equipment that will help divers to be always aware of their partner's location in water, which would increase safety and facilitate communication in this context. Devices popularly known as the "Buddy Finder" are going to include built-in GPS technology of water immersion optimized thus guaranteeing the signal reliability underwater. It will be able to monitor the distance between partner divers and give updates on the positions in real-time. There are particular distances such as about 5m where if a diver drifts from his/her buddy then the device will vibrate to give an alert. This innovation was created for divers so that they can have more confidence and fewer cases of orientation loss during the dive, as well as increase the safety of the divers through a comfortable and easy use of the system that would allow them to locate their companions seamlessly during the dives.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The "buddy finder" wrist device is made from Polyurethane rubber, and has better strength and flexibility, housing essential electronics like a GPS module for location tracking, a Bluetooth module for communication, and a microcontroller to process data. It features a rechargeable lithium-ion battery, a vibration motor for alerts, LED indicators, and an adjustable strap for comfort. Development involves creating 3D models, assembling components, and programming firmware alongside a companion mobile app for user interface and messaging. After field testing for GPS accuracy and battery life, user feedback is incorporated before preparing for mass production while ensuring quality and safety standards are met.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Novelty and Uniqueness

"Buddy finder" is a unique wrist-connected device designed to increase social interaction and ensure safety among friends. It features GPS tracking for real-time location sharing, Bluetooth connectivity for proximity alerts and vibration notifications to help users find each other in crowded places. With an emergency SOS button for added safety and a customizable design for personalization, it caters to a variety of social events and outdoor activities. A companion mobile app further enriches the experience by allowing messaging and setting meeting points. While it promotes security and social engagement, potential drawbacks include battery dependency and privacy concerns.

3.2 Benefit to Mankind

Wrist-mounted buddy locators offer many benefits, improving security and communication. They help locate individuals in an emergency, ensuring the safety of children in crowded places. These devices enhance real-time communication between groups during outdoor activities, fostering social interaction and encouraging a more active lifestyle. Additionally, they often include health monitoring features that track fitness and alert users to vital sign abnormalities. The compact and user-friendly friend finder integrates with smartphones for added functionality and provides peace of mind for families by enabling location sharing. Overall, they promote personal safety and a healthier lifestyle, making them a valuable technological addition.

3.3 Potential of Commercialisation

The potential for commercialization of wrist-mounted buddy locators is huge due to growing security concerns and the increasing popularity of wearable technology. As consumers seek enhanced security for themselves and their families, these devices can cater to diverse markets, including outdoor recreation, travel and senior care. Technological advances in GPS and sensors enable the creation of feature-rich products, while integration with smartphones makes them even more attractive. Customization options and subscription services for premium features further increase market appeal. Partnerships with schools and organizations can also expand visibility, positioning friend finders as an important tool for personal safety and connectivity.

4. DISCUSSION

The invention of the Buddy Finder device addresses the importance of diver safety and encourages the buddy system while diving. Using the device, which has real-time GPS tracking, vibration notification and Bluetooth proximity alert, aims to enhance diver awareness toward buddies and improve safety during underwater exploration.

One of the main advantages of the Buddy Finder is its potential to strengthen the buddy system, which is essential during scuba diving as it helps in lowering accidents and improving emergency response. This device will send an alert when a diver drifts too far from their buddy (in % meter) which will reduce the risk of separation and raise awareness for the buddy in a low visibility environment. This device also alerts their buddy about gas supply issues or disorientation.

Buddy Finder also wasn't limited to scuba diving. It can also be used as a tracking device for children and adults during outdoor activities which shows how versatile this device can function. Expanding its target market beyond just diving to include some outdoor activities like hiking or kayaking, will increase its value to the market. Its design also focuses on user comfort so that it would not hinder the user's daily activities and can still be used for casual wear.

The collection of data for this project was conducted using Google Forms, an online survey tool. The data was presented below from 50 respondents.

Do you think our product would be useful to you?
50 responses

Figure 1. The chart indicates that 86% of respondents find the device useful for them while 14% do not.

Are you satisfied with the current features of our product?
50 responses

Figure 2. The chart shows that 76% of respondents are satisfied with the current feature provided by the device while 24% do not.

Would you consider purchasing our product in the future?
50 responses

Figure 3. 90% of respondents show interest in purchasing the product in the future while 10% do not.

Based on the data that we collected from the Google form, we could see that we got an overall positive response from our product. This shows that this product has value in the market, especially a device that provides safety precautions to the user.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Buddy Finder device shows great potential to enhance diver safety while exploring underwater by improving awareness and communication between diving partners through real-time GPS tracking, vibration alerts and keeping track of the distance between diving partners. The usage of this device will greatly enhance the buddy system, which is important in reducing accidents underwater and helping in a fast response for underwater emergencies in a low visibility underwater environment.

The Buddy Finder was not limited to divers only as it could also be used for outdoor activities or for casual wear, which makes it a versatile device, greatly enhancing its appeal. From the survey data that we collected, the market shows a great interest in the device proving its usefulness, ease of use and market appeal. The majority of the responses are positive, showing the strong desire from the respondents to purchase it. This shows that the Buddy Finder device has some practical value and potential success in the market.

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